

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Retrieving nucleotide sequencing data from the European Nucleotide Archive
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	3 April 2025
Time of event	1-3pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) is the European node of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration (INSDC), providing a comprehensive record of the world's nucleotide sequencing information, covering raw read sequencing data, sequence assembly information and functional annotation. The three INSDC members (ENA, NCBI-SRA and DDBJ-SRA) routinely exchange data which ensures nucleotide data is archived and shared across geographically dispersed locations (Europe, USA and Japan). The ENA is provided by EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute, EMBL-EBI.</p> <p>This workshop provides an introduction to the ENA data and metadata model and data retrieval tools, followed by an opportunity to practice retrieving a range of different data types from the ENA using a variety of tools and protocols.</p>
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outline the ENA data and metadata standards • Identify the metadata fields associated with different data types submitted to the INSDC • Build queries based on the datasets you would like to retrieve • Describe of the range of tools offered by the ENA to download data files • Practice data retrieval using the ENA advanced search
Format description	<p>Hands-on workshop, online via Zoom.</p> <p>Dr Joana Pauperio and Maira Ihsan led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in retrieving data from ENA. Participants then had the chance to apply these skills in follow along activities.</p> <p>Questions were managed using a living document.</p> <p>Participation was subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>
Audience	This workshop is for Australian life science researchers and bioinformaticians working with nucleotide sequencing data. It is suitable

	for researchers who are interested in accessing, downloading and using data retrieved from the ENA.
Prerequisites	Some of the data retrieval methods demonstrated make use of the command line. Using these command line methods during the workshop is optional. If you wish to try them out we recommend having a basic understanding of how to interact with the command line.
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Google document (living document) was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • A terminal emulator (the built-in Mac and Windows versions are sufficient) for methods requiring the command line.
Lead Trainers	<p>Dr Joana Pauperio, Biodiversity Curator, European Nucleotide Archive, EMBL-European Bioinformatics Institute</p> <p>Maira Ihsan, User Support Bioinformatician, European Nucleotide Archive, EMBL-European Bioinformatics Institute</p>
Training materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slides that introduce the ENA metadata model and provide an overview of methods of data retrieval from the ENA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ ENA_data_retrieval_slides.pdf • A practical guide that provides step by step instructions on how to retrieve data from the ENA <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ ENA_data_retrieval_practical.pdf
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/ena-nuc-retrieval-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Data retrieval http://edamontology.org/operation_2422
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au